

Synthesis Analysis for Statistical Methods: A Scoping Review

Rabeya Illyas Noon¹, Nan Hu², Michelle M. Hospital²

^{1,2}Department of Biostatistics, Robert Stempel College of Public Health & Social Work, Florida International University, 11200 SW 8th St, Miami, FL 33174

Abstract

Background: Synthesis analysis, which is derived from meta-analysis, can determine the consistency and robustness of findings across different populations and settings.

Objective: The objective of this study is to conduct a scoping review to identify and map the comprehensive extent of available research on methodological and applied synthesis for different statistical responses.

Method: Eligible studies, such as peer-reviewed articles published in English between 2000 and 2025 that presented methodological innovations and applied examples relevant to a range of statistical outcomes were included. Searches were systematically conducted across major databases. Articles were excluded if they did not provide sufficient methodological detail for implementation or if their primary focus was not on the analysis of statistical models.

Results: A total number of 248 studies were identified. Among these, 7 studies met the inclusion criteria.

Conclusion: Synthesis analysis extension improves risk estimation and statistical power and reduces biases. Extending synthesis analysis to survival data is a novel meta-analytic approach that allows for a more comprehensive synthesis of public health studies.

Key Words: Meta-analysis, synthesis analysis, prediction model, multivariable analysis, time-to-event outcome, public health studies.

1. Background

The term “meta-analysis” was coined by a statistician named Gene V. Glass in 1976 [1]. Glass defined meta-analysis as “analysis of analyses” [2]. Meta-analysis refers to the results presented by combining and analyzing data from different studies conducted on similar research topics [3]. In terms of statistical methods, meta-analysis is defined as a statistical technique for amalgamating, summarizing, and reviewing previous quantitative research [4]. The primary objective of meta-analysis is the ability to increase statistical inference and provide more precise estimates of the effect size by pooling data from multiple smaller studies [5]. However, meta-analytical methods rely on sufficient, consistent data across individual studies [6].

To address this gap, a multivariate meta-analytic modeling method called “synthesis analysis” was proposed, which refers to the challenge of integrating information from studies that lack complete multivariate data [7]. In statistics, synthesis analysis is a methodology that constructs a multivariate regression model by integrating univariate regression coefficients and pairwise correlations from multiple independent studies or data sources [4]. The advantage of using synthesis analysis is that it can enhance the consistency and robustness across different populations and settings [7]. A thorough understanding of synthesis analysis practices in public health can help identify existing challenges and support efforts to improve the reporting and interpretation of statistical outcomes. Therefore, a scoping review has been conducted to systematically examine how synthesis methods are currently applied and analyzed in the literature.

2. Methods

This review was conducted per the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist and explanation (<https://www.prisma-statement.org/scoping>).

The electronic databases PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus were searched. Studies have been used in the search by using the following keywords: "synthesis analysis," "meta-analysis," "linear model," "logistic model," "combining statistical models," "multivariate model," and "prediction model." Studies were included in this review if they met the following criteria: (1) the study was published as a peer-reviewed journal article; (2) the article presented a methodological development and applied examples of the synthesis method applied for statistical outcomes; (3) the publication appeared between the years 2000 and 2025; (4) the manuscript was written in English. Exclusion of studies was determined by specific eligibility parameters such as (1) the article described synthesis analysis, or meta-analysis, without providing sufficient methodological or applied detail for implementation; (2) the primary objective of the method was not the analysis of statistical responses.

3. Results

The initial database search in Google Scholar, PubMed, and Scopus identified 248 studies as potentially relevant. After removing the duplicates, the screening process included titles, abstracts, and method sections to further narrow down the search. Of these, only 7 studies published between 2004 and 2017 addressed methodological and implementation research across various contexts of synthesis analysis included to contribute to this review.

The selected articles were reviewed, and relevant data were manually extracted and organized into a tabular format. The extracted data included authors, year, methods, outcome types, goals, and key findings. The collected details were summarized and presented in a tabular format. The table simplified the identification of methodologies, techniques/applications, advantages, and disadvantages within the investigations.

3.1 Methodological Synthesis

Sources	Methods	Outcome type	Goal	Key findings
Samsa et al. (2005) [7]	Matrix synthesis of univariate β s using correlation and SDs	Continuous	Derive multivariate models from disparate study data	Effective for prediction; less accurate for coefficient estimates
Becker & Wu (2007) [8]	Generalized Least Squares (GLS) for combining regression slopes	Continuous	Address methodological challenges in synthesizing regression coefficients	Introduced GLS approach; noted metric incompatibilities and model diversity as core limitations
Zhou et al. (2009) [4]	Improved synthesis analysis (non-normality, variance estimation)	Continuous	Build multivariate models from partial univariate data	Enhanced robustness; applied to SHD risk modeling with superior performance

Sheng et al. (2014) [9]	Logistic-specific synthesis integrating univariate models + correlations	Binary	Extend synthesis analysis to prediction models with binary outcomes	Mathematically sound; outperforms prior methods in accuracy and generalizability
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Table 1: Overview of available methods for methodological synthesis

3.2 Applied Synthesis

Sources	Methods	Outcome type	Goal	Key findings
Jackson et al. (2011) [10]	Multivariate random-effects model with covariance structure	Continuous, Binary	Promote use of multivariate models for correlated outcomes	Improves estimation efficiency; requires caution due to assumptions and complexity
Tang et al. (2013) [11]	Two-step synthesis: effect size unification + weighted estimation	Mixed (SMD, OR etc.)	Combine findings from diverse meta-analyses	Created unified synthesis framework; matches full-study meta-analysis performance
Hu et al. (2014) [12]	Synthesis analysis combining Framingham Stroke Risk Score (FSRS) with seven literature-derived risk factors	Binary	To enhance stroke risk prediction by integrating additional risk factors into the Framingham Stroke Risk Score (FSRS)	All seven added risk factors significantly contribute to stroke risk prediction

Table 2: Overview of available statistical applications for synthesis analysis

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the synthesis analysis extension enhances risk estimation and statistical power, mitigates biases, and optimizes temporal, labor, and financial efficiencies. The results of this study indicate that the synthesis method is limited to continuous and binary outcomes.

As of now, no research has proposed or evaluated a synthesis framework for time-to-event or survival data, which are crucial for medical research and clinical decision-making. [13]. In the absence of a synthesis analysis approach for time-to-event outcomes, critical information from various incomplete studies is underutilized, constraining our capacity to deliver robust, evidence-based survival predictions and enhance patient care [14]. Therefore, broadening the statistical parameters of synthesis analysis, while enhancing efficiency and transparency, will be essential for wider application in public health research.

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